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Research Article

Development of a rapid LC method for Metopimazine based on a Quality by Design (QbD) approach

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ABSTRACT

Aim: Develop and implement a highly effective, reliable, precise, and validated analytical method for analyzing Metopimazine in both bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms, utilizing a quality-by-design (QbD) approach. **Background:** Metopimazine, an antiemetic drug, has limited research in analysis. Comprehensive analytical technique design and validation are necessary for efficient, rapid, and accurate qualification in pharmaceutical dosage form. **Objectives:** A novel and efficient reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method was developed and validated for analyzing Metopimazine in its bulk form and pharmaceutical preparations, employing a quality-by-design (QbD) strategy. **Materials and methods:** Box Behnken Design experimental trial, analyzed using Design Expert® software, determined that retention duration, peak symmetry, and NTP (number of theoretical plates) were the determining variables for Critical Analytical Attributes (CAAs). The actual experimental data corresponded with the predicted data. **Results:** The optimized chromatographic conditions involved a mobile phase of Methanol: Water 45:55 v/v with pH maintained at 3.5 and a flow rate 1 mL/min. Furthermore, the oven temperature was set at 25°C, with a 266 nanometer. The stationary phase was HiQsil C18 (250 x 4.6 mm i.d., 5 μ) column and the detection was carried out using a PDA detector with a run time of 6 minutes. In order to validate the method, parameters such as linearity, specificity, precision and accuracy were evaluated. **Conclusion:** A high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) method was successfully developed and validated to determine the concentration of a drug in bulk and tablet forms, adhering to the acceptable standards outlined in the ICH guidelines.

INTRODUCTION

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Metopimazine is an Antiemetic agent chemically known as 1-(3-[2-(Methylsulfonyl) phenothiazin-10-yl]propyl)-4-piperidine carboxamide. It refers to the phenothiazine drug class, which also includes tricyclic compounds containing nitrogen and sulphur.¹ Pale yellowish white crystalline powder, insoluble in water, soluble in DMSO (Dimethyl sulfoxide) and methanol, melts at 170.5°C.^{2,3,4} A method for estimating Metopimazine, which involves chromatographic separation by using a fluorescence detector, and HPTLC analysis.^{5,6} Quality by Design (QbD) is a rigorous manufacturing process in pharmaceutical industry, with ICH Q11 [2] for drug substance development and ICH Q8 [1] for pharmaceutical development.^{7,8} According to QbD's definition, it is "a systematic approach to development that begins with predefined objectives and emphasizes understanding and control, based on sound science and quality risk management." This method provides a reliable, well-planned, method that serves its intended function and works as expected throughout its lifecycle.^{9,10,11,12} The literature review reveals insufficient research on Metopimazine analysis, indicating the need for improved techniques. There is no RP-HPLC method for determining Metopimazine in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form using quality-by-design approach. The present study was done to develop a simple, reliable, precise, and validated method for the analytical determination of Metopimazine in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form using the analytical quality by design approach.^{13,14}

Figure.1 Metopimazine Structure²⁻⁴

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chemicals and Reagents:

Metopimazine was provided as a gift sample by Micro Lab Thane. The 7.5 mg Vogalib tablet used in the commercial dose formulation was purchased from Cephalon Pharmaceutical Co. in Mumbai. All the chemicals and reagents used for analysis like acetonitrile, methanol was HPLC grade and procured from Merck Chemicals in India.

Instrumentation:

The determination of Metopimazine was conducted using an HPLC (JASCO LC System-1200 series) equipped with an autosampler, column oven, and wavelength detector. This system features a photodiode array detector, a quaternary pump, and a Rheodyne injector with a 20 µL loop. Separation was achieved using a HiQsil C18 column (250 x 4.6 mm i.d., 5 µm). Before quantification, the column was consistently saturated with the solvent system to ensure effective separation, with this process repeated each time prior to analysis.

Procedure for Standard Stock Solution: A standard stock solution was prepared by accurately weighing 100 mg of Metopimazine into a 100 mL volumetric flask and diluting it with methanol to achieve a concentration of 1000 µg/mL. An aliquot of 1 mL from this standard stock solution was further diluted with methanol in a 10 mL volumetric flask to obtain a sub-stock solution with a concentration of 100 µg/mL.

Preparation of Solution and Selection of Wavelength: One milliliter (1 mL) of the sub-stock solution (100 µg/mL) was taken and diluted to 10 mL with methanol, resulting in a 10 µg/mL solution. This solution was scanned across the 400 to 200 nanometer range, identifying the maximum absorbance at 266 nanometers.

Procedure for Sample Stock Solution: For the sample stock solution, twenty tablets were accurately weighed and ground into a fine powder.

An amount equivalent to 10 mg of Metopimazine was calculated, transferred to a 100 mL volumetric flask, and diluted with methanol. The mixture was sonicated for 15 minutes. From this solution, 1 mL was taken and diluted to 10 mL with methanol to achieve a concentration of 100 µg/mL.

Optimization of Mobile Phase:

To identify the optimal mobile phase, several solvents with various compositions were examined.

Table.no.1List of Mobile Phase Compositions examined

	Mobile phase	Ratio	Remark
1.	ACN: Water	50:50	Poor resolution, Shoulder peak
2.	Methanol: Water	50:50	Peak absent
3.	Methanol: Water	55:45	Peak broadening
4.	Methanol: Water	60:40	Peak Splitting
5.	Methanol: Water	70:30	Poor resolution
6.	Methanol: Water	75:25	Peak broadening
7.	Methanol: Water (pH:3.5)	70:30	Peak Splitting
8.	Methanol: Water (pH:3.5)	50:50	Peak tailing
9.	Methanol: Water (pH:3.5)	45:55	Peak was symmetric

Chromatographic Conditions

Before usage, the mobile phase of a 45:55 Methanol:Water mixture with pH maintained at 3.5 was filtered, degassed, and sonicated. The stationary phase was a HiQsil C₁₈ (250 x 4.6 mm i.d., 5). A thermostatically controlled column oven maintained the column's temperature at 25°C. The flow rate was kept constant at 1 mL/min. The flow rate was maintained at 1 mL/min. The injection volume was 10 µL, and detection was carried out using a PDA detector set to 266 nanometers.

Experimental Design:

The experimental design was developed using Design-Expert software version 10 to examine various variables and verify the method's performance. The composition of mobile phase A, the composition of mobile phase B, and the flow rate were identified as the Critical Method Parameters (CMPs) for the execution of the experiment. Table.no.2 presents the qualified values of the variables analyzed. Retention duration, peak symmetry, and the number of theoretical plates were employed in the experimental design as Critical Analytical Attributes (CAAs) that were controlled and

expected to affect method outcomes. For the experimental plan, a 3³-factorial design with three components at three levels was taken into consideration. The initial approach involved using the Box-Behnken design, but it was later determined that the process is non-linear. Table 3 presents the experimental observations and the Design of Experiment (DOE) plan.

Assessing the results of the experiment and determining the final conditions for the method:

The experimental design included 13 runs with various method conditions, which were assessed for retention time, peak symmetry, and the number of theoretical plates. A response surface Box-Behnken statistical screening strategy was employed to optimize and evaluate the main effects, interaction effects, and quadratic effects. Design Expert® (Version 10.0, Stat-Ease Inc.) was used to explore quadratic response surfaces using a 3-factor, 3-level design.

Table.no.2 Independent variables: factors and levels

Factors	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Composition of mobile phase A	40	45	50

Composition of mobile phase B	50	55	60
Flow rate	0.95	1.00	1.05

Table.no.3 Box Behnken Design Plan and Responses

Std	Run	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Response 1	Response 2	Response 3
		A: Composition of mobile phase A	B: Composition of mobile phase B	C: Flow rate	NTP	Retention time	Symmetric factor
5	1	40	55	0.95	2416	7.135	1.712
1	2	40	50	1	2972	6.813	1.722
4	3	50	60	1	1908	6.824	1.724
13	4	45	55	1	3065	6.547	1.5
3	5	40	60	1	2604	6.916	1.839
6	6	50	55	0.95	2616	7.135	1.712
12	7	45	60	1.05	1014	5.613	1.204
9	8	45	50	0.95	2924	7.218	1.818
2	9	50	50	1	2417	6.932	1.618
10	10	45	60	0.95	1097	7.323	1.832
11	11	45	50	1.05	2165	5.71	1.11
8	12	50	55	1.05	2221	5.521	1.211
7	13	40	55	1.05	1093	5.418	1.096

Method Validation:

Through laboratory testing, method validation is a technique for analysis that establishes if the procedure's performance characteristics meeting the requirements for the intended analytical implementation. The method's specificity, selectivity, linearity and range, accuracy, precision, robustness, limit of detection, and limit of quantitation were all assessed in accordance with the ICH Q2(R1) guidelines.

System suitability:

System suitability testing was done to determine the instrument's acceptance requirements. The percentage relative standard deviation (% RSD) of various components, such as retention time, asymmetry, and theoretical plates, were

calculated. There should be no more than 2.0% RSD throughout five replicates.

Linearity:

The slope, intercept, and correlation coefficient data were used to evaluate the linearity of Metopimazine within the concentration range of 2-12 µg/mL.

Precision:

The precision for the preferred method was calculated. Results of precision analysis reveal that the proposed approach is precise and that its %RSD was below the limit (below 2%), with a standard deviation of less than 2.

Accuracy:

To verify the accuracy of the method, an analysis of recovery from a commercial formulation was conducted at three standard addition levels. The

recovery percentage of Metopimazine was determined, with a standard deviation of less than 2, indicating the method's accuracy. The percentage of recovery was found to be 99.98%. The relative standard deviation (RSD) was calculated to ensure that the data met the permissible limits.

Specificity:

The interference of any potential degradation products has been studied to assess the specificity. The solutions for the test sample and the standard were both scanned separately in the 200–400 nanometer range.

Robustness:

By varying the mobile phase's composition and wavelength, the three dilutions were examined under various conditions. Calculations were used to determine the assay's % RSD.

Assay:

Twenty tablets were accurately weighed and ground into a fine powder for the Metopimazine assay. A quantity of 50 mg of the powder was estimated and transferred to a 50 mL volumetric flask, diluted with methanol, and sonicated for 15 minutes. Next, 1 mL of the resulting stock solution was transferred to a 10 mL volumetric flask and diluted with methanol to prepare a solution with a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. A 1 mL aliquot of this solution was then transferred to a 10 mL volumetric flask and diluted with methanol to obtain a solution with a concentration of 10

$\mu\text{g/mL}$. For HPLC analysis, 10 μL of the specified dilution was injected.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The proposed work developed and evaluated an RP-HPLC technique for estimating Metopimazine in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. Metopimazine consequently showed good solubility in the initial solvent that was selected for it. Additionally, the chromatographic conditions were examined, and the parameters were defined. Metopimazine demonstrated a high peak in the mobile phase Methanol: water (45:55) with pH maintained at 3.5 with a retention time of 6.53 minutes.

Implementation of Qbd:

The statistical analysis of the experimental observations was conducted using Design Expert® software (Version 10.0, Stat-Ease Inc.) with the Box-Behnken design. The inputs utilized by the software are presented in Tables 5 and 6.

Thirteen runs were selected to be done once the design was implemented and inputs were put into the software. A statistical assessment regarding the degrees of freedom (Table.no.7, Table.no.8, and Table.no.9) as well as a contour plot of retention time, standard error of design, and symmetric factor, as shown in Figures 4, 5, and 6, were generated after the 13 runs were finished. The software was provided with the responses, considering retention time, peak symmetry, and NTPs (number of theoretical plates).

Figure.2 Chromatogram of Metopimazine using Methanol: Water (45:55) at pH 3.5

Table.no.4 Optimization of Chromatographic Conditions

Parameters	Results
Column	HiQsil C18 (250 x 4.6 mm i.d.,5)
Flow rate	1.0 mL/minute
Detector	PDA
Detector wavelength	266 nm
Injection volume	10.00 µL
Retention time	6.53 minute
Mobile phase	Methanol: Water (45:55) with pH maintained at 3.5

Method Validation:

Linearity

For the concentration against area graph, the Metopimazine showed a correlation coefficient of 0.9998, a slope of 1795.7, and a y-intercept of 226.33. The drug indicated linearity between the concentration range of 2–12 µg/mL, as shown in Figure 6.

Precision

As observed in Table.no 12, the precision results reveal that the suggested method is accurate because the standard deviation is less than 2.

Accuracy

Table. no. 11 illustrates the accuracy results. The standard deviation was less than 2, indicating that the method is accurate, and the percentage recovery was 100.69.

Table.no.5 Box-Behnken design description for optimization

Study type	Response surface
Design type	Box-Behnken
Design model	Quadratic
Runs	13

Table.no.6 Description of the Box-Behnken design's optimisation strategy

Factor	Name	Units	Type	Subtype	Minimum	Maximum
A	Composition of mobile phase A	%	Numeric	Continuous	40	50
B	Composition of mobile phase B	%	Numeric	Continuous	50	60
C	Flow rate	mL/min	Numeric	Continuous	0.95	1.05

Table.no.7 Analysis of the degrees of freedom

Response	R1	R2	R3
Name	NTP	Retention time	Symmetric factor
Observation	13	13	13
Analysis	Polynomial	Polynomial	Polynomial
Minimum	1014	5.418	1.096
Maximum	3065	7.323	1.839
Ratio	3.02268	1.35161	1.67792
Model	Linear	Quadratic	Quadratic

Table.no.8 Result of optimized chromatographic method

Response	Parameter	Observed Analysis		Inference
		p-value	r-value	

		(<0.05)	(-1 to +1)	
R1	NTP	0.1623	0.2252	Not significant
R2	Retention time	0.0003	0.9985	Significant
R3	Symmetric factor	0.0239	0.9126	Significant

Figure.4 Retention time contour plot

Table.no.9 Obtained solutions for optimized condition

Run	Std	A: Composition of mobile phase A	B: Composition of mobile phase B	C: Flow rate	NTP	Retention time	Symmetric factor
13	4	45	55	1	3065	6.547	1.5

Linearity:

Table.no.10 Data of linearity

Sr.no.	Concentration	Peak Area
1	2 µg/mL	1994
2	4 µg/mL	3856
3	6 µg/mL	5616
4	8 µg/mL	7362
5	10 µg/mL	9279
6	12 µg/mL	10961

Figure.5 Standard error of Design contour plot

Figure.6 Contour plot of Symmetric factor

Figure.6 Linearity curve of Metopimazine Accuracy:

Table.no.11 Data of accuracy

	Sample	Standard	Total Conc.	Peak Area	Calculated Conc.	%Recovery	Mean	SD	%RSD
80%	4	3.2	7.2	6767	7.193051	99.782	100.29	1.314	1.310
	4	3.2	7.2	6826	7.257112	101.78			
	4	3.2	7.2	6753	7.17785	99.307			
100%	4	4	8	7544	8.036699	100.91	100.61	1.050	1.043
	4	4	8	7490	7.978067	99.451			
	4	4	8	7565	8.059501	101.48			
120%	4	4.8	8.8	8271	8.826059	100.54	101.19	0.644	0.637
	4	4.8	8.8	8300	8.857546	101.19			
	4	4.8	8.8	8328	8.887948	101.83			
Overall average		100.69							
Overall SD		1.002							
Overall % RSD		0.996							

Precision:

Table.no.12 Data of precision

Sr.no.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Area	
		System Precision	Method Precision
1.	10	8711	9971
2.	10	8781	9896
3.	10	8422	9754
4.	10	8689	9880
5.	10	8602	9978
6.	10	8807	9695
Mean		8668.667	9862.333
Standard Deviation		140.8896	115.2123

Relative Standard Deviation	0.016253	0.011682
% Relative Standard Deviation	1.625274	1.168205

Robustness:**Table.no.13 Data of robustness**

			1.	2.	3.	Mean	SD	%RSD
Flow rate	0.95	Area	10305	10310	10304	10306.33	3.21455	0.03119
		Rt	7.600	7.613	7.608	7.607	0.006557	0.086203
		Ntp	3512	3524	3543	3526.333	15.63117	0.44327
	1.05	Area	11410	11408	11399	11405.67	5.859465	0.051373
		Rt	4.942	4.95	4.962	4.951333	0.010066	0.203308
		Ntp	2221	2245	2230	2232	12.12436	0.543206
Temperature	25	Area	8878	9480	8968	9108.667	324.7173	3.564927
		Rt	6.436	6.500	6.492	6.476	0.034871	0.538468
		Ntp	3089	3099	3082	3090	8.544004	0.276505
	35	Area	11733	11789	11452	11658	180.5852	1.549024
		Rt	6.142	6.110	6.209	6.153667	0.050521	0.820984
		Ntp	3961	4013	3986	3986.667	26.00641	0.652335
Wavelength	264	Area	12886	12709	12621	12738.67	134.9679	1.059514
		Rt	5.525	5.642	5.497	5.554667	0.076918	1.38474
		Ntp	2784	2807	2821	2804	18.68154	0.666246
	268	Area	12456	12553	12159	12389.33	205.286	1.656957
		Rt	5.708	5.704	5.716	5.709333	0.00611	0.10702
		Ntp	2827	2817	2878	2840.667	32.71595	1.1517

Assay:**Table.no.14 Outcomes using the HPLC method for determining the dosage of Metopimazine in tablet**

Tablet formulation	Label claim(mg/tab)	Estimated label claim (mg/tab)	% purity
Metopimazine	7.5 mg	6.9 mg	99.97%

CONCLUSION:

The current QbD research was carried out to examine the results of many variables and to assess method performances. This present study emphasises the application of the analytical QbD method in the development of a reliable RP-HPLC technique to analyse Metopimazine. The experimental results assisted in identifying high-risk CMPs (Column temperature, flow rate, and mobile phase ratio) and their effects on CAAs

(retention time, symmetric factor, and a number of theoretical plates). The validated parameters all satisfied the requirements defined in the ICH guidelines. Metopimazine was estimated using an effective, precisely calculated, and reliable HPLC approach for both bulk and its tablet dosage form.

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